

Recommended citation: Hansen, P. S. (2018). Error patterns in first-year students' answers to mathematical assignments as observed 2010-2018. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 840-847). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672712.

Error patterns in first-year students' answers to mathematical assignments as observed 2010-2018

Per Skafte Hansen, M. Sc. Eng., Ph. D.
Associate professor at DTU
E-mail: psha@dtu.dk

To Merete

Keywords: Error pattern, feedback, learning model, layered instruction

ABSTRACT

An analysis of 1600+ one-page feedback sheets written by the author (in response to hand-in answers from comparable groups of first-year engineering students to assignments in a 20 ECTS points mathematics course) seeks to identify and classify error patterns. Three major patterns appear prominent: 1) The transfer problem: failing to apply, or wrongly applying, methods erstwhile learned in other areas; 2) The contingency problem: wrongly attaching a property of an example or mnemonic to a general problem; and 3) The failure to correctly use or extend logical conditions. Along with these are others that may be considered variations, but are probably best treated on their own, such as the general issues of failure to separate related, but different, concepts; of failure to make use of specific arguments over general ones (or vice versa); the blindness to the lucky/unlucky choice; and of failure to distinguish between a mathematical entity and its name. These, too, may deserve to be called 'patterns'. Finally, there is the universal 'Thinking fast and slow' (Kahneman) phenomenon: If a task resembles a known one, a previously successful method is attempted, whatever the outcome. The pedagogical/didactical response to an error pattern should be a manifestly layered instruction, distinguishing operational guidance from invitation to reflect upon a deeper meaning, that must needs be expressed in terms somewhat distant from the subject directly at hand. This is akin to Argyris' 'single-loop, double-loop' learning theory, which may be supplemented by the simple, but useful, five-step learning model fact→relation→operation→insight→innovation to make it explicit to students that they may have wrong or unfortunate patterns to unlearn and useful ones to internalize.

INTRODUCTION

Providing feedback on hand-in assignments is an important part of the instruction of students, whether in the engineering disciplines or elsewhere. Since September 2010, the author has annually instructed teams of 1st year students and marked up their assignments in a 20 ECTS point course in introductory mathematics. By writing the feedback in a fixed-format one-page scheme and storing the digital version, the author has collected a 1600+ page log of typical comments. From 2010 to summer 2014, hand-ins were written or printed on paper and the marked-up essays returned to the students along with a print-out of the feedback page. From autumn 2014 onwards, most hand-ins have been electronic, allowing storage of 600+ essays for further analysis.

The goal of the present paper is to find and characterize **error patterns** in the students' mathematical writings. What is meant by an 'error pattern' will – so it is hoped – gradually become clear, since no simple definition is available. The course itself, the format of the feedback sheets, and the general concept of a 'pattern' and its resemblance and contrast to an 'error pattern' are briefly described to provide a background. The disarmingly simple method of analysis and the main result, identification of important patterns, follows. A discussion of possible utilizations of the findings so far – drawing primarily on other observations from teaching engineering students - as well as of intended further analysis forms the last part of the paper.

I BACKGROUND

The course: 01005 *Advanced Engineering Mathematics 1* is a 20 ECTS points introductory mathematics course, mandatory for B.Sc. Eng. students at DTU. The course covers calculus and linear algebra and comprises (2017-18) 2 lectures, 3h tutorials and 3h groupwork per week along with thematic exercises and a 3-week project. The duration is 13 + 13 weeks (winter and summer terms) and the assessment comprises 7 homework assignments, tests in fall curriculum, separate examination in the 3-week project course and tests in spring curriculum. The exams (December and May) are 1+2 hours. Throughout the course, intense use is made of CAS tools, for which on-line tutorials and examples are provided, along with video streaming of the lectures and various other e-learning items. The present author serves as supervisor of the tutorials and marks up the 7 assignments for one class of students each year, and in addition prepares, oversees and instructs in a repetition course in August prior to the re-examination of the 70-100 unlucky individuals who failed the May exam. A class typically consists of 35 students and the number of individual supervisors is accordingly 30+, some catering for two classes. Over the period 2010-2018, the various numbers and conditions have varied slightly: Classes have consisted of up to 40 students, there has been as many as 10 assignments in a year, etc.; but the above is a reasonable outline.

The feedback sheets: Each supervisor develops his or her own style, i.e. the one described here is unique and admittedly somewhat elaborate. In evaluations, student almost uniformly praise the thoroughness of this kind of feedback – and almost uniformly deplore the time spent by the author writing down the many sheets. —

The format, developed from the outset with no specific purpose in mind other than the provision of a just distribution of comments and instructions, comprises (apart from administrative information):

- 1) Copies of the ‘learning goals’ stated in each assignment. These learning goals, each one or two lines long, are marked with a selection of symbols printed in red: ☺, ✓, (✓), ·, -, —, ⊗, indicating a decreasing degree to which the goal was met
- 2) Numbered comments, the numbers referring to similar numbers and brief indications written in the essay during the first pass of markup
- 3) An overall assessment (in words) + a Roman numeral I-V (the only “officially” required feedback
- 4) Hints for improvement

The ‘learning goals’ are a given part of each assignment, typically specifying what the assignment is about, but also with at least two addressing the use of illustrations and the need for clear and precise writing. The numbering of comments and the brief remarks in the essays arise during the first pass through the hand-ins and are thus specific for the individual essay. The comments as well as the assessment and the hints are written in the second pass. They are likewise individual, although use is occasionally made of sheets of standard comments, when an assignment causes many identical errors or mishaps. The assignments typically comprise 10-12 individual questions forming 3-4 problems. There is some year-to-year reuse and variation, but the majority of problems are new from year to year, and although an “official” answer is distributed to the supervisors, most – the author included – work out a solution of their own for use during the mark-up process.

A few words on the concept of a ‘pattern’: Over the years it has become increasingly clear to the author – who also teaches and has taught a variety of other courses in mathematics and topics with a strong leaning towards mathematics – that a common vocabulary is needed for the description of related problems that can be observed in hand-ins and during oral exams when students grapple with abstractions or the words expressing them. Perhaps the best common name for what is sought

for is ‘error pattern’; and the subsequent sections attempt to provide a few handfuls of descriptions of such patterns, distilled from the above-mentioned feedback sheets.

The first that comes to mind in response to the word ‘pattern’ is probably *geometric patterns*, be they discrete (e.g. Grünbaum and Shepard [10]) or continuous (e.g. [11]), with the less regular markings of animals a close second [16]. Psychologists and sociologists speak of *patterns of behavior* (e.g. [9]), and architect Christopher Alexander went a step further and based his *design patterns* on his understanding of *life patterns* [1]. Inspired by Alexander’s ideas, the “GOF Book” (“Gang of four”, [8]) carried the idea of a design pattern into programming as a kind of meta-template, suitable for object-oriented programming. Lately, the concept of a ‘design pattern’ has spread into many walks of life, including education (e.g. [15]). Other than behavioral and design patterns, a third non-geometrical use of the word is important to what follows: *logical patterns* may be either of a mathematical nature (e.g. [2]) or more in the line of philosophical analysis of argumentation (e.g. Flew [7]).

As for the phrase itself, *error patterns* are discussed in [3], [6], [17], [18] and others, all of them providing valuable information and inspiration, but none of them the perhaps rather low-level tool sought for by the present author.

Finally, it should perhaps be mentioned that none of the above writers offer a concise definition of the word ‘pattern’, Grünbaum and Shepard even deploring its vagueness. We shall have to contend ourselves with the words of Green ([9] p. 147):

Finding patterns within the networks that underlie events and relationships can provide useful information. Particular kinds of networks have patterns of connections that make their presence felt in the way systems behave.

and rely on the sweeping generalization of Wikipedia: ‘A pattern is a discernible regularity in the world or in a manmade design’.

II THE STUDY AND THE METHOD

The data has already been described: 1600+ feedback sheets in a fixed format, each containing from 3 to some 15 comments on the quality and merits of a statement, paragraph, section and/or totality of a hand-in essay answering (part of) one of the 10-12 questions in the assignment.

These sheets have been assembled, grouped by assignment and the comments then analyzed. Whenever a comment seemed to have a bearing on a problem deeper than a slip, a misreading, a syntax error in the use of the CAS tool etc., it was copied to a document, still sorted by assignment. These comments were further analyzed and a sub-selection made, now under headings that eventually became the general names of the patterns, as described below.

Three important parts of the analysis was the repeated re-naming of the patterns, the shuffling of comments as the patterns crystallized, and the matching of the last batches of comments to what had become the canon. It should perhaps be emphasized that no attempt will be made at a statistical analysis, since all information is of a qualitative nature and almost every comment unique. Also: At the time of writing this, only 903 sheets have been filtered through the complete cascade of selection and sorting as the identification of patterns and their manifestations seems to have reached a point of stability. Completion of the filtering task is planned as part of step 2, briefly described below, which will also involve revisiting the 600+ essays preserved electronically.

IV PATTERNS OBSERVED

Without further ado, here are the patterns observed, presented with a number and name, described as succinctly as possible and illustrated by the (admittedly sometimes rather indirect) evidence of a few of the extracted comments:

1.1 The transfer problem: This has generated a substantial literature, e.g. [14], where we also find as good a definition as we can hope for:

[...] research on transfer has demonstrated the difficulty of enabling students to recall and apply their science knowledge in novel situations

If, for 'science' we read 'mathematics', and if 'situations' has as general a meaning as possible, we have a useful concept of this pattern. If context A requires/allows operation c , but only the part a of A is truly necessary, the student may be unable to use c in context B, even if a is also part of B. The problem appears to lie in the *conditioning* aspect of learning. Even if a is pointed out, the triggering of the use of c is not elicited: In the mind of the student, c is too strongly linked with the totality of A.

- Du skal faktisk runde *op* [Actually, you should use the *ceiling value* of the number]
- Men hvad véd du allerede om egenværdier? [But what do you already know about eigenvalues?]
- Du lader definitionen gælde uden for cirkelns afgrænsning [You extend the definition to let it hold outside the circle]
- Men de sidste to polynomier er kun lineært uafhængige af hinanden. Når de kombineres med $4 - x$ er der *tre* polynomier, hvoraf kun *to* er lineært uafhængige [But the latter two polynomials are only mutually linearly independent. When they are combined with $4 - x$ there are *three* polynomials, of which only *two* are linearly independent]

In these four examples, the student either fails to recognize 'a', extends 'a' or 'A' to a 'B' where operation c cannot be used, or unwittingly creates a situation where the 'A' must be restored or a 'super-A' must be created and 'super- c ' developed.

Already here, we begin to see the need for a concept of **error patterns**: If the feedback merely corrects the specific error, the student may never reflect upon its nature and therefore miss an opportunity to learn. The error made by the student must be recognized as something deeper than a slip and the comment must elicit reflection. (As can be gathered, the author is biased towards 'Socratic examination').

1.2 Mixed narrative: Continuing in the notation employed above, we may find that the context is B and the operation c , but part of the narrative deals with elements of A either not present or not relevant.

- Det ser lidt mystisk ud på dette sted; men alle udregningerne på næste side er O.K., nærmest som om du først har overvejet én fremgangsmåde og så er skiftet til en anden [This spot looks a bit mystifying; but all calculations on the following page are O.K., as if you had first considered one procedure, then changed to another]
- Og hvad er så den afgrundsdybe forskel på en implicit cirkel og en eksplicit cirkel? (Dette minder mig om en af mine yndlingstegninger: to ret ubestemmelige skikkelser ligger i skyggen af et stort træ, og den ene spørger: Precisely what is the difference between a goblin and a hobgoblin?) [And what is the deep difference between an implicit circle and an explicit circle] etc
- Du skriver det, som om egenvektorerne er lineært uafhængige hver for sig; men det er altså en egenskab ved det samlede sæt [You write as if eigenvectors are linearly independent, each on its own; but it is a property of the assembly]

The first case is a straightforward example. In the second, the student introduces a distinction (implicit/explicit) that does not apply and goes on to argue two cases where only one exists. The third is quite common, assigning a property to the wrong level of a hierarchy.

The mixed narrative pattern deserves a deeper study as it is often interlaced with one or more of the other patterns. There is, nonetheless, reason to grant it status as a full pattern in its own right.

1.3 The contingency problem, a kind of mirror image of the transfer problem: “c can be applied, so A must be the context”, whereupon A is enforced on B or assumed implicit. There are two further complications: The student may *fail* to impose the reduction of the context that makes c applicable; or there may have been an interlude, where a narrow context was superimposed. (Here, an example is necessary to explain what is meant: The student may have learned Taylor expansion, then – some time later – have learned how to analyse stationary points by means of Taylor expansions, then, upon return to a general framework, have established so strong a mental link that ‘an expansion point’ is identified with ‘a stationary point’ or *vice versa*).

The contingency problem has its own literature, e.g. [5], [19]. It can be tricky to spot and almost impossible to correct, because the student will cling to what has once been learned and fail to discover or appreciate the need to *unlearn* some of it.

- Disse sammenhænge er tilfældige [These connectios are fortuitous]
- Dette gælder [kun] for symmetriske matricer [This only holds for symmetric matrices]
- Sæt $y = 1$ (konstant), så reduceres funktionen til et tredjegradspolynomium i x [Let $y = 1$ (a constant), then the function is reduced to a third degree polynomial in x]
- Nej, altså: hvis t er konstant, er der ikke tale om funktioner. Tænk igen! [No, really, if t is a constant, there is no function involved]

The first is the general case, the second a specific instance. The third is the variant discussed above, which typically require very clear instructions. The fourth is almost paradigmatic: The letter “t” usually denotes a variable, setting a train of thoughts in motion that has no bearing on the subject at hand.

A final difficulty concerning the contingency problem is that it seems to be absent from literature on mathematics teaching – and little known in Danish educational literature in general. —

2.1 The wrong perspective: This is possibly the most difficult pattern to spot, diagnose and remedy. It may take the form of *overkill*, a kind of “underkill” (a detail hides the general picture), a failure to expressly meet a learning goal, or simply an emphasis on an irrelevant part of the problem or context.

- Sært: først finder du stjernefunktionen korrekt – og så finder du en ”stamfunktion”, der bare skulle have været stjernefunktionen?? [Strange: First you find the star function correctly – then you find a function primitive, which should simply have been the star function??]
- Igen-igen: dette er en opgave i matematik, ikke en øvelse i at bruge Maple og tro, at man har fundet svaret, bare Maple har fundet et svar [Once again: This is a mathematics assignment, not a Maple © exercise carrying the bonus that one has found *the* answer if Maple © has found *an* answer]
- Her slipper du til gengæld ikke: det fremgår tydeligt af læringsmålene, at du skal vise at du behersker Taylor’s formel med rest [Here you won’t go free: It is clear from the learning goals that you must demonstrate mastery of Taylor’s formula with a remainder]

2.2 Mixed concepts: Mathematics has itself to blame for many instances of this, the most common error pattern. “Abuse of notation” and re-use of notation is tolerable among experts but wreaks havoc with the mind of the innocent. The use of the word ‘vector’ is the standard example: Other than being a 2D/3D object known from physics (a *geometric vector* is drawn as an arrow, but really is a representative of an equivalence class), a ‘vector’ can be a member of an abstract vector space or – *horribile dictu!* – the wrongly applied reference term meaning a row or column matrix. To trump this, polynomials are sometimes considered members of a vector space with the natural basis “1, x , x^2 , ...”, elements are written as $p(x)$, and mappings as $x \cdot p(x)$, etc. The author once wrote a four-page step-by-step explanation of a three-line quiz problem, painstakingly unwinding the rapidly changing meanings of the letter x as a number, a variable, a vector, a function, etc.

- Uha-uha: her lader du x -erne (kaldet a) indgå i afbildningsmatricen og gør dermed afbildningen ikke-lineær. [Uh-oh: Here you let the x 's (called a 's) be part of the mapping matrix, this making the mapping non-linear]
- Der skal skelnes mellem et (lineært) funktionsudtryk og ligningen for planen, også selv om de ligner hinanden til forveksling [One must distinguish between a (linear) function expression and the equation of the plane, even if they are confusingly similar]
- Funktionen indgår ikke i beregningen af massemidtpunktet, der alene er en egenskab ved området [The function is not involved when calculating the mass mid-point, solely a property of the domain]
- Nej, da: fortegnet flytter sig ikke pludselig over på modulus [No – no: The sign doesn't suddenly jump from argument to modulus]

2.3 The incomplete narrative: This has proud historical precedences, cf. Kummel's and Wiles' struggles with the Fermat theorem. The name refers to the gap in the argumentation, especially when it represents the crucial element of a proof or derivation. Other manifestations are the circular argument, the (attempted) proof by figure, proof by example, proof by meta-example (an example cleverly disguised in symbols) and Flew's No-True-Scotsman-Move (where a too-general statement is defended by explaining away obvious counterexamples).

This is by far the most common error pattern and also the one that has generated the longest comments. One very short and one rather long example will have to suffice:

- Jamen 1 og 1 er da ikke forskellige? [But 1 and 1 are not different?]
- Du får aldrig svaret på 'Hvorfor?' [You never get around to answering the "Why?"]
- Skriv en samlet "historie", der kan læses fra den ene ende til den anden. Kunsten er så at kun være detaljeret omkring de væsentlige udregninger – dvs. vise detaljer første gang, eller når noget er usædvanligt, osv. – og at holde et flow, så der er en begyndelse, en midte og en slutning [Write a complete "story" that can be read from one end to the other. The art, then, is to include details only when describing essential calculations – i.e. to show details on their first occurrence on when something is unusual, etc. – and to maintain a flow, thus creating a beginning, a middle and an end]

3.1 The argument is about the wrong issue: Almost ironically, this is fairly easy to detect, but frustrating to mark up/correct, as the comment must contain most of the argument about the *right* issue, leaving comparatively little room for reflection.

- Njah, altså: alle tre områder er udsnit af en kugle, det er derfor, de har samme form for parameterfremstilling [Well, all three domains are sections of a massive sphere, which is why they have related parameterizations]
- Ved ordet "grænseværdi" forstås bare tallet [Here. The word limit only refers to the number]
- Mærkeligt svar: først finder du en, så argumenterer du for, at der er uendeligt mange, og heraf konkluderer du, at der ikke er en... (-!?) [Strange answer: First you find one, then you argue that there are infinitely many, and from this you conclude that none exists]

3.2 The validation-verification dichotomy: See [4]. The distinction can prove surprisingly hard to keep clear. The popular version is:

Verification: *Are we doing this is the right way?* (And thus getting the right results)

Validation: *Are we actually doing the right thing?* (The 'sanity check' – I am indebted to Rune Bundesen for this)

Students are encouraged to add a verification, whenever possible. This may range from a simple estimate to a complete calculation using a different method. The problem arises, of course, when they somehow manage to confirm a wrong result.

- I betragtning af din grundighed: prøv at vænne dig til at tænke: "Hvordan kan jeg checke resultatet på en anden måde?". Det vil både fjerne de ærgerlige fejl og give dig yderligere forståelse af stoffet [Considering your thoroughness: Try to get used to thinking "How can I check the result in a different way?". This will eliminate wexing errors and add insight into the matter at hand]
- Det er ikke sikkert, solve har fundet alle løsninger [One cannot be sure that solve has found all solutions]

At the end of the day, there is a vast difference between getting the right thing wrong and getting the wrong thing right. —

3.3 The empty pattern: This is added, even though it is rarely applicable to the individual (non-) answer. The missing or almost missing answer can take many forms – no text, sporadic text, genuinely nonsensical text, etc. – but can only be analysed in case of repetition. In other words, one can look for patterns of the kind “What is not answered?”, “When is the text garbled?”, “Is there some kind of method in the madness?”

- Selve den sproglige formulering er volapük – men udregningerne er gode nok [The formulation is volapük, but the calculations are sound]
- ...og det samme gælder grafen (-?-) — — 4a) Nej, jeg læste det hele igennem igen: du har totalt misforstået: du ændrer søjlerne, men du skal ændre rækkerne. At det kommer til at gå op, har en anden algebraisk forklaring: rangen af en matrix er lig rangen af dens transponerede [...and the same goes for the graph (?) — — No, I read the whole thing again: You have completely misunderstood. You change the columns, where you should change the rows. That the whole thing fits together has a different explanation: The rank of a matrix equals the rank of its transposed]

The choice of numbering: The reader will have guessed that the patterns numbered **1.x** are considered the most serious or significant, the patterns numbered **3.x** the least. Also **y.1** denotes a blockade or slide, while **y.2** is a mix-up and **y.3** an incompleteness. As more patterns emerge, this numbering is likely to change.

Emerging patterns: Some errors have been observed, but not yet in such numbers that their ontological status can be finally judged: Effects of too strong a faith in a (sometimes self-chosen) ‘authority’ (such as the instructor giving an ambiguous instruction...), failure to follow a procedure, “Laplacian arrogance”, i.e. stating that something is clear, which isn’t – and a really difficult-to-handle failure to observe, what a text actually says, caused, it seems, by an unprepared mind.

Last words on patterns: In several of the patterns – almost all of them, in fact – we recognize the “jumping to conclusions”-way of solving mathematical problems that many students develop during their high school years (Danish *Gymnasium*), where many are among the brightest and find mathematics easy. When confronted with university level mathematics, they must often adapt a new attitude. This process is wittily described in [13].

V DISCUSSION

Students should learn about error patterns and should be given feedback that points out very clearly to them that “This is just a slip”, “This is serious, a 3.1 Argument about the wrong issue”. This, of course, requires that a common language describing error patterns is developed and applied by their instructors and supervisors.

In the opinion of the present author, still more can be achieved by also designing the instruction around a sufficiently simple learning model, allowing lecturers to say, and assignments to state: “This is just rote learning, this is operational drilling, this is for deeper reflection”. Whenever possible, the author suggests a simple five-step ladder:

fact → relation → operation → insight → innovation

where it is to be understood that you are not expected to *first* learn all the facts, *then* learn all the relations, etc. Quite the contrary, you learn a few facts, then a few relations between these, then the

first operation, then go back for more facts, etc. This may seem trite; but anyone who has reflected upon his or her own teaching will occasionally have come across times where one or more steps was skipped or passed too quickly. To quote [12]: You can *present* facts, *prove* relationships, *demonstrate* operations and *tell* about your own insight; while innovation may perhaps be *inspired*.

If instruction is presented in an explicitly layered form, addressing each of these clearly and with feedback stating equally clearly when it is time for the individual student to simply correct a slip or oversight or practice a method somewhat more, versus when it is time to reflect upon an error pattern that must be rooted out, a deeper, better learning can be achieved at very little extra cost — or such is the hope of the present author.

CONCLUSION

When this project was initiated, the hope was to provide simple words and phrases denoting error patterns in first-year engineering students' learning of mathematics. Such patterns had shown themselves with still greater clarity in hand-in answers to assignments and were echoed in the feedback. Analysing a fairly large number of feedback sheet written in a fixed format, the author has so far found nine such patterns. There could well be many more, and the search is still on.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alexander, C., *The Timeless Way of Building*, OUP 1979
- [2] Beck, Matthias and Ross Geoghegan, *The Art of Proof*, Springer 2014
- [3] Dole, S., Applying Psychological Theory to Helping Students Overcome Learned Difficulties in Mathematics, *School Psychology International* **24**: 95-114, 2003
- [4] Dybkaer, R., 'Verification' versus 'validation': a terminological comparison, *Accred. Qual. Assur.* **16**: 105-108, 2011
- [5] Elsner, B, and Berhard Hommel, Contiguity and Contingency in Action-Effect Learning, *Psychological Research* **68**: 138-154, 2004
- [6] Fiori, C., and L. Zuccheri, An Experimental Research on Error Patterns in Written Subtraction, *Educational Studies in Mathematics* **60**: 323-31, 2005
- [7] Flew, Anthony, *Thinking about Thinking*, Fontana 1975
- [8] Gamma, E. et al, *Design Patterns*, Addison-Wesley 1994
- [9] Green, D. G., *Of Ants and Men*, Springer 2014
- [10] Grünbaum, B. and G.C. Shephard, *Tilings and Patterns*, Freeman 1989
- [11] Hammer, Ø, *The perfect Shape*, Springer 2016
- [12] Hansen, P.S., A personal Bildungs-Environment, *Online Educa* 2009
- [13] Kahneman, D., *Thinking Fast and Slow*, Penguin Books 2011
- [14] Martinuk, M., et al., Research Projects in Introductory Physics: Impacts on Student Learning, *Physics Education Research Conferences* (Sabella et al. (ed.)), American Institute of Physics, 2009
- [15] Mor, Y. et al., *Practical Design Patterns for Teaching and Learning with Technology*, Sense Publishers 2014
- [16] Murray, J.D., *Mathematical Biology*, Springer 1989
- [17] Saunders, K.J. et al., Adventitious Reinforcement of Maladaptive Stimulus Control Interferes with Learning, *Behav. Analysis Practice*, **9**: 223-229, 2016
- [18] Smith, G., CAL: Improved Learning and Improved Teaching, *Comput. Educ.* **10**: 115-118, 1986
- [19] Thomas. G.V., Contiguity and Contingency in Instrumental Conditioning, *Learning and Motivation* **14**, 513-526, 1983